

Stability Constants of some Bivalent Metal Ions with *N*-(Phenyl and 2/3/4-Hydroxyphenyl)diacetylmonoxime in Water—Ethanol Medium

P. P. HANKARE*^a, A. H. MANIKSHETE^a, R. S. RAMPURE^a and L. P. DESHMUKH^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, ^bDepartment of Electronics, Shivaji University, Centre for P. G. Studies, Solapur-413 003

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The chelating properties of Schiff bases of aldehydes and ketones are well established. These ligands show useful analytical as well as biological activities¹. In the view of this, the present communication reports the synthesis of the Schiff bases from diacetyl monoxime and substituted anilines. The stability constants of their chelates with bivalent Cu, Ni, Co, Zn and Mn have been determined pH-metrically by Calvin-Bjerrum technique as adopted by Irving and Rosotti² in 50% (v/v) water-ethanol medium at ionic strength $I=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄) and temperatures 30, 40, 50°.

The structure of Schiff base derived from *o*-aminophenol and diacetylmonoxime is shown below.

Protons marked with asterick undergo dissociation upon coordination and azomethine nitrogen, O of oxime and O of phenolic group are bonding atoms.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand stability and metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by half-integral and graphical methods². The values of average stability constants are given in the Table 1. From the titration data n_A values were calculated and plotted against pH to obtain values of pK_{NOH}^H , pK_{OH}^H and pK_{NH}^H . These values were further corroborated by linear plots of $\log(1-\bar{n}_A)/\bar{n}_A$, $\log(2-\bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A-1)$ and $\log(3-\bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A-2)$ versus pH. DAMO-A has only one dissociable proton whereas for DAMO-*o*-AP, DAMO-*m*-AP and DAMO-*p*-AP have two dissociable protons, one of the oxime group and another the phenolic group. In addition to these pK_{NH}^H values correspond to the dissociation of proton initially associated with azomethine group. Therefore

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS (log K)

Ligand	Cation	B at temperature (°C)			
		30	40	50	
DAMO-A	H	10.45	10.25	10.00	
	H	3.50	3.35	3.15	
	Cu	9.72	9.43	9.18	
	Cu	8.92	8.60	8.38	
	Ni	9.01	8.64	8.51	
	Ni	8.10	7.84	7.64	
	Co	8.38	8.22	8.00	
	Co	7.29	7.00	6.92	
	Zn	8.05	7.82	7.58	
	Zn	6.68	6.38	6.26	
	Mn	6.95	6.72	6.58	
	Mn	5.96	5.80	5.58	
	DAMO- <i>o</i> -AP	H	11.30	11.02	10.89
H		9.93	9.70	9.55	
H		3.78	3.65	3.50	
Cu		9.04	8.52	7.98	
Ni		8.04	7.56	7.12	
Co		7.20	6.56	6.28	
Zn		6.46	5.90	5.68	
Mn		5.78	5.32	4.94	
DAMO- <i>m</i> -AP		H	11.40	11.12	10.95
		H	10.00	9.85	9.65
	H	3.90	3.71	3.56	
	Cu	9.04	8.84	8.42	
	Ni	8.28	7.80	7.36	
	Co	7.08	6.76	6.36	
	Zn	6.54	6.04	5.78	
	Mn	5.86	5.52	5.30	
DAMO- <i>p</i> -AP	H	11.90	11.43	11.25	
	H	10.35	10.05	9.83	
	H	3.90	3.70	3.53	
	Cu	9.70	8.84	8.50	
	Ni	8.30	7.82	7.54	
	Co	7.40	6.78	6.68	
	Zn	6.98	6.34	5.75	
	Mn	6.12	5.64	5.32	

the formation curves extended over the range of DAMO-A (1) ($1.98 > \bar{n}_A > 0.09$), DAMO-*o*-AP (2) ($2.84 > \bar{n}_A > 0.08$), DAMO-*m*-AP (3) ($2.84 > \bar{n}_A > 0.04$) and DAMO-*p*-AP (4) ($2.84 > \bar{n}_A > 0.05$). The results are accurate within ± 0.2 units. Hence pK values of compounds 2–4 are higher than compound 1. The pK values for compounds 2–4 are in the order of $2 > 3 > 4$. These compounds have hydroxyl substituent at *ortho*, *meta* and *para* positions respectively. The observed pK values for these compounds can be explained on the basis of electron-withdrawing inductive ($I-$) effect and electron-releasing mesomeric ($M+$) effect of the OH group. It seems that the electron-releasing mesomeric effect ($M+$) plays a dominant role in determining the pK values. The increased electron density at N results in increased pK values of all the three compounds. If only ($M+$) effect is considered then compound 3 should have lower pK value than compound 2 as the latter has OH group in *ortho*-position as against in *meta*-position in the former. It is plausible that electron-withdrawing ($I-$) effect of hydroxyl group is responsible for lower pK values of compound 2 to that of compound 3.

From the metal titration curves \bar{n} and pL values

were calculated; the \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values, to get the formation curves of metal complexes as log K_1 and log K_2 . These are further corroborated by linear plots of log $(1 - \bar{n})/\bar{n}$ and log $(2 - \bar{n})/(\bar{n} - 1)$ against pL. These results are accurate within the ± 0.03 log units. The order of stability constants in metal complexes of ligands have been found to be $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$, which is in good agreement with the order found by Irving and Williams³.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Ethanol was purified by the standard procedure⁴. The ligands were synthesised by a reported procedure⁵ and their purity was checked by tlc method. Double-distilled water was used for preparing the solutions of metal perchlorate. Solutions of Schiff bases *N*-phenyldiacetylmonoxime (DAMO-A) (1), *N*-(2-hydroxyphenyl)diacetylmonoxime (DAMO-*o*-AP) (2), *N*-(3-hydroxyphenyl)diacetylmonoxime (DAMO-*m*-AP) (3) and *N*-(4-hydroxyphenyl)diacetylmonoxime (DAMO-*p*-AP) (4) derived from diacetylmonoxime and substituted anilines were prepared by using standard procedure.

An Elico LT 120 pH-meter equipped with combined glass electrode was used. The pH-meter was calibrated using the appropriate standard buffers with necessary corrections. The readings of pH meter in 50% (v/v) water-ethanol were corrected for solvent effect⁶. In order to calculate the thermodynamic parameters, the titrations were carried out at temperatures 30, 40 and 50° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). Nitrogen purified by Fieser solutions and passed through the same solvent as used in the cell, was bubbled through the cell solution to provide both stirring and inert atmosphere. The Schiff base metal solutions of ionic strength $I=1.0M$ (controlled with NaClO_4) were made up in solvent and titrated against solutions of NaOH (0.098 M). All titrations were performed at least twice and replicate values of pH always agreed to within 0.01 pH unit.

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